

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

MIGRATION- PARTICIPATION: CHALLENGES OF THE GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE IN BRAZIL AND IN THE EU

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POLICY STATEMENT

The increasing centrality of citizens in post-modernity is reflected in the complementarity of representative democracy with other models of participatory-deliberative-multicultural democracy, in which citizens acquire greater prominence and power regarding the definition of public policies. In Brazil, since the 1988 Constitution, a governance structure has been consolidated by combining Inter-managerial Commissions (structures of bi/tripartite negotiation and celebration of agreements for policy management) with policy councils (collegiate structures) and conferences (structures for social participation). Despite the adverse context, since the Maastricht Treaty of 1992, as a supranational federation, the European Union, by establishing a two-tier system of government, faces the challenge of creating arenas of political participation – building a supranational democracy while lacking a federal constitution – capable of simultaneously promoting territorial cohesion, enhancement of the interior, cross-border cooperation, and political-administrative decentralization. Both in Brazil and in the EU, an institutional structure of political participation has been built to attend, among others, to the demands of migrants and refugees. In this process, their participation in the dimensions of political concerted decision-making is a *sine qua non* condition for the democratic legitimacy of the country where they live.

BACKGROUND

A democratic State is one that allows the participation of the people in power, shaped by the extent of the popular will and legitimated by the consensus of the generality of its citizens, guaranteeing a minimum set of rights to all who are in its territory. The fact that immigrants do not have political rights, even though they are permanent residents in the country, creates a situation of potential democratic deficit during the drafting of any migration policy, since there is no possibility of equal participation of those directly affected by these instruments discussed. To surpass the deficit, it is necessary to consider the tension between difference and equality, recognizing the legitimacy of minority groups to place their collective interests within the public sphere – in a context of multicultural democracy in which social justice would come from the equal participation of all members of the community in the promotion of

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redistributive policies (1) - having the right to be heard and being entitled to benefits that solve disparities related to their specificities (2).

From the public sphere to the political sphere, the gathering and articulation among different actors guarantees the legitimacy of their resolutions and the necessary democratic character of the institutional spheres created to be part of the political system. Regarding the consultation spheres for public decision making, the policy councils are permanent collegiate structures, of a consultative and deliberative nature, integrating the basic structure of the Public Administration body, aiming to reduce the separation between government and society as well as to promote greater convergence between government decisions and social demands.

In relation to public forums, public policy conferences are instruments that combine the participation of government and civil society representatives in discussions and deliberations on a given theme with the aim of proposing guidelines for the drafting of public policies. The Inter-managerial Commissions, on the other hand, are structures of negotiation and celebration of agreements for the implementation of the National System of the sectorial policy and for agreements related to the operational aspects of its management. The Tripartite Interagency Commission is the structure for articulation among federal, state, district, and municipal managers to make feasible the implementation of the National System of the sectorial policy, constituting itself as the main structure of negotiation and celebration of governmental actions, concerning the operational aspects of the management of the decentralized and participative system. It is organized at a federal level and is equally composed by representatives of the three spheres of the government, considering the country's regions (3).

As a new venue for society to participate in the management of public policies, policy councils, public policy conferences, and inter-managerial committees are challenged to be democratic structures designed to achieve three main objectives: to promote the construction of citizenship and political education; to enable the identification and permanent registration of society's demands; and to exercise social control over the government. As a concrete demonstration of the new relations between civil society and the state, these institutions become a rich object of study for the issue of governance in countries of the global south and north, specifically, in Brazil and in the European Union, despite the adverse context of the latter (4). In the case of the migration issue, the great challenge is to create strategies to include citizens and "non-citizens", that is, immigrants and refugees who move into a territory related to a state entity, imposing their presence and their freedom of movement against the sovereign power of the state, geographically based on its limits (5). In the context of the globalized world, it is therefore a matter of innovating in the construction of supranational democracy and cosmopolitan citizenship.

FINDINGS

In Brazil, since the 1988 Constitution, the management councils, the public policy conferences, and the inter-managerial commissions have become important institutions in the realm of public policy. These structures of political participation linked to education, health, culture, environment, migration, among many other sectors, have spread throughout the Brazilian municipalities and states. This process results

from the constitutional principles that prescribe the participation of society in the conduction of public policies, from the regulatory legislations that establishes these participatory structures as invariably conditions to the transfer of federal funds and from the decentralization process (6).

In the case of participatory structures linked to migration, in 2013, the National Secretariat of Justice, linked to the Ministry of Justice, created a Commission of experts to discuss and propose a draft for a new Migration Law considering the Foreigners Statute, a law of securitizing character, drafted during the Military Dictatorship, and that hinders the integration of the migrant.

The first National Conference on Migration and Refuge (7) followed an inclusive model with broad participation of those interested in the topic, through the election of 556 delegates representing Civil Society, migrants, and government agencies in numerous local and regional events with broad discussion of topics related to migration and refuge, in addition to participation via the internet, through the *Participa Brasil* platform. The suggestions from I COMIGRAR were taken to the Commission whose work entailed the project with five main characteristics: making the legislation compatible with the 1988 Constitution and Human Rights treaties, transforming the national security paradigm to a humanistic approach, creating systemic coherence in migration legislation, listening to Civil Society, and preparing Brazil for contemporary international migration (8).

Nevertheless, this bill has not been submitted to the Congress. The new migration framework derives from the bill proposed by the Senator Aloysio Nunes. Despite having gone through several public discussions, this new migration framework fell short the legislative proposal built with civil society from the beginning. Even so, the repeal of the Foreigners Statute, the basis of migration policy for thirty-seven years, occurred with the enactment of the Migration Law 13.445 of May 24th, 2017, changing the statist and securitizing logic to a more humanistic approach of migration. The immigrant, however, is still neglected in his condition of "social and political subject capable of participating politically in public decisions, being necessary, therefore, the institution of structures to promote this participation in all federal entities" (9).

The National Immigration Board (1980) is a deliberative body constituted by representatives of the government, employers, workers, and civil society that has broad competencies related to the drafting of national immigration policy. According to Meunier (10), the CNIg is an important structure for interactions, consultations, and information exchange that reinforces, along with seminars, events, and workshops, the development of the political community on migration – of which are part not only government actors, but also other sectors of the state, civil society, private sectors, academia, and international organizations. On the other hand, the National Board of Refugees – CONARE (1997) aims to recognize and make decisions about refugee status in Brazil, and to promote the local integration of this population. It is a multi-ministerial body in which participate the government, civil society, and the UN, through the UNHCR.

In this context, states and municipalities have been creating their policy committees and councils to deal with refugee and migrant issues in Brazil. At a state level, Rio Grande do Sul, Minas Gerais, Rio de Janeiro, Distrito Federal, São Paulo, Amazonas, Mato Grosso do Sul, and Goiás have councils and committees to promote participation, ensure promotion, and protect the rights of refugees, migrants, and stateless persons (11). Nevertheless, it is in the state of São Paulo that the Municipal Board of Immigrants (CMI) stands out for being the only public body in Brazil that allows immigrants to apply, vote and be voted,

playing an important role of inclusion and effective participation of this population in the proposition, and monitoring of public policies (12). With UNHCR support, Congolese refugee Hortense Mbuyi took a seat at the CMI in São Paulo in 2021 (13).

In the European Union – EU (political system based on a community of states, establishing a two-tier system of government of federal type) the European Commission, with a supranational character, acts actively, with political independence, in the areas of legislation, policy, and action programs, and is responsible for implementing the decisions of the European Parliament and the Board of the European Union, striving for transparency and efficiency (14). However, promoting popular participation for effective integration of the European citizen, as a source of political legitimacy of the EU's power, in everyday political life, has been a challenge.

The Lisbon Treaty (2007) introduced procedures to integrate citizens. In addition to the mechanisms of the institutional system adopted by the European Union (popular participation in the democratic decision-making process, such as the right to vote and to be voted, among others), the Europe for Citizens 2014-2020 and Rights, Equality and Citizenship 2014-2020 programmes have strengthened democratic participation at the European level by aiming, respectively, to improve knowledge about the European Union, its history and diversity, and to support projects for equality and fundamental rights.

The Pact of Amsterdam (2016) entailed the Urban Agenda for the EU with the aim of finding responses to the problems facing European cities with a focus on the themes: air quality; circular economy; climate change adaptation; digital transition; energy transition; housing; inclusion of migrants and refugees; responsible and innovative public procurement; employment and skills in the local economy; sustainable land use and nature-based solutions; urban mobility and urban poverty (15).

Regarding the inclusion of migrants and refugees, the European Commission, in partnership with representatives of cities, national governments, and civil society organizations have prioritized common actions to promote integration. For this purpose, it was created the European Website on Integration; Migration became a priority, and it was established a European Agenda for Migration. Under the umbrella of the Urban Agenda for the EU, the first phase of the partnership took place in the period 2016-2019. Among the main results of the partnership are the creation of the European Migrant Advisory Board, a self-directed group of advisors with immigrant and refugee backgrounds, providing advice on integration issues, and the Urban Academy in Integration, an integration training program for policy makers in cities and regions.

The issue of migration and refugeeism is also the focus of the 2021 Conference on the Future of Europe, a series of citizen-led conversations and debates that will allow people from all over Europe to share their ideas and help define the common future of European citizens. Through the Multilingual Digital Platform, created for any European to share their ideas, and the Citizens' Panels (1) at both European and national levels, contributions will go to the Conference Plenary (2), a new public forum that seeks to provide a structure for debate with citizens on important priorities and challenges.

Under the theme Predictable, balanced, and reliable migration management, discussions of migration issues, according to the leaders, "call for a modern European migration and asylum system, border management, cooperation with partner countries and the fight against smuggling of migrants. They also involve the protection of people fleeing violence and the integration of newcomers into society" (16). For this purpose, they indicated the following categories for proposals: 1) Asylum and migration; 2)

Integrated border management; 3) Deepening international cooperation; 4) Legal migration and integration.

In the case of member states, Portugal presents the Council for Migration – CM (2014), formerly the Consultative Board for Immigration Affairs – COCAI (1998), as a body for consultation, support, and participation in defining the general lines of action of the High Commissioner for Migration ACM and in the decision-making of the Directive Board, ensuring the participation and collaboration of public and private entities in the definition and implementation of migration policies.

The structure of political participation, which is beginning to be outlined in the EU, is similar to that which has already been consolidated in Brazil – and to some extent also in Portugal (17), as institutional structures for political articulation. Nevertheless, besides the improvement from the point of view of the quality of participation, it is necessary to think about expanding and consolidating instances of parity participation for the political forwarding of migrants' and refugees' demands.

CONCLUSIONS

The practice of good governance recognizes that common problems require joint actions with states and so-called expanded participation. A broad institutional framework is being built that enables the participation of civil society in the three spheres of the federation in the conduct of public issues and policies in countries of the global south and north. However, when it comes to the issue of migration, political decentralization needs to advance.

In the case of Brazil, conferences, councils and committees at the federal level, and some initiatives at the state and municipal levels, with São Paulo standing out, need to be analyzed from the point of view of the quality of participation in terms of the provision of information and the promotion of communication channels that are fundamental for decision making and effectiveness. Regarding the EU, through the Commission's initiatives in the framework of the Urban Agenda for EU and especially the public debates carried out by the Conference on the Future of Europe, the issue of migration has been gaining prominence and some instances of participation have been established such as the European Migrant Advisory Board. However, systemic decentralization, from the supranational level to the member states and from these to the municipal levels, is still to be built to surpass the democratic deficit linked to the migration issue.

SUGGESTIONS

- To further study the decentralization structure existing in Brazil and in the EU considering, in specific, those directed to the participation of migrants and refugees in order to better comprehend it.
- Where there is no structure of parity participation, indicate the creation and where they exist, strengthen the governance structure and strengthen the relationship with national and supranational levels.

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ⁱⁱ Four panels, each with 200 European citizens chosen by random selection in the 27 Member States, were organized to reflect on the diversity of the EU in terms of: geographical origin (nationality and urban/rural background), gender, age, socio-economic background, and level of education; each panel has at least one citizen per Member State; one third of each panel is composed of young people (aged 16-25). Available <<https://futureu.europa.eu/pages/reporting?locale=pt>>. Accessed on February 6th, 2022.

ⁱⁱⁱ This structure of political articulation discusses the recommendations of the national panels and the European Citizens' Panels, and the contributions of the multilingual digital platform, grouped by themes, without predefined results. After these recommendations have been presented by the citizens and discussed with them, the Plenary submits, on a consensual basis, its proposals to the Executive Board. The latter drafts a report in full collaboration and transparency with the Plenary. The Conference Plenary is composed of 108 representatives of the European Parliament, 54 of the Council, three of the European Commission, 108 representatives of all national parliaments, on an equal level, and 108 citizens: 80 representatives of European Citizens' Panels, 27 of national citizens' panels or Conference events (one per Member State), as well as the President of the European Youth Forum. Also participate 18 representatives of the Committee of the Regions and 18 of the Economic and Social Committee, 6 elected representatives of regional authorities and 6 elected representatives of local authorities, 12

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representatives of the social partners, and 8 representatives of civil society. Available <<https://futureu.europa.eu/pages/plenary>>. Accessed on February 6th, 2022.